

"IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF LEARNING FOR LEARNERS USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE METHODS ON ONLINE TEACHING PLATFORMS"

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Abstract: *This article focuses on the relevance of artificial intelligence (AI) in learning foreign languages, in particular, English, its importance and the possibilities of its wide use in the field of education. It also discussed the prospects of artificial intelligence, which is rapidly developing today, in classrooms and auditoriums, and in general, in the field of education.*

Keywords: *artificial intelligence (AI), foreign languages, AI in teaching foreign languages, information technologies, automation of the educational process.*

Introduction

The concept of Artificial Intelligence (AI) dates back to ancient civilizations, but its foundations as a scientific discipline emerged in the mid-20th century. The term "Artificial Intelligence" was first introduced by John McCarthy during the Dartmouth Conference in 1956, which is considered the birth of AI as an autonomous field. Initially, AI was applied to programming computers to follow rules and make decisions (acting as human experts). However, this approach had its limitations.

Thus, in the 1980s, AI shifted its focus to machine learning algorithms. In simple terms, AI refers to the ability of computer systems to perform creative and intellectual activities that were previously unique to humans. It encompasses highly complex and advanced fields, such as neural networks, machine learning, natural language processing, cognitive computing, and computer vision. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Sh. M. Mirziyoyevning 2020 yil 5-oktabrdagi "Raqamli O'zbekiston — 2030" strategiyasini tasdiqlash va uni samarali amalga oshirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi 6079-sonli farmoni va On

February 17, 2021, Resolution No. 4996, titled "On measures to create conditions for the accelerated implementation of artificial intelligence technologies," was adopted. This resolution provided an opportunity to systematize and organize activities in this field.

Notably, the "Action Plan to Improve the Position of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the Artificial Intelligence Readiness Index" was approved as part of this initiative. The plan places particular emphasis on the development and application of AI technologies in economic sectors, social spheres, and the public administration system. Special attention is given to introducing these technologies into areas such as agriculture, energy, healthcare, and e-government systems.

Advantages of Using Artificial Intelligence in Language Learning

The use of artificial intelligence (AI) in language learning offers numerous benefits, making the process not only more efficient but also engaging and convenient. Below are the key advantages of incorporating AI into language learning:

1. Personalized Learning Programs

AI enables the creation of learning programs tailored to the learner's skill level, strengths, and weaknesses. This allows each student to learn a language in the most effective way for them. As a result, the learning process aligns with individual needs, helping learners acquire necessary skills faster and more effectively.

2. Availability Anytime, Anywhere

Applications powered by AI are accessible at any time and from any location. Learners can study languages at their own convenience, making the process more flexible and accommodating. Without being restricted to school hours or classroom settings, students can practice at times that suit their schedules best.

3. Self-Assessment and Real-Time Analysis

AI-driven applications can analyze a learner's progress and mistakes in real time. For instance, they can detect errors in pronunciation or written communication and provide immediate feedback. This allows learners to quickly identify and correct their mistakes, accelerating the learning process.

By leveraging these advantages, AI significantly enhances the language learning experience, making it more tailored, accessible, and effective for learners worldwide.

Improving Pronunciation

AI can evaluate and analyze users' pronunciation to help them improve. For example, AI-powered programs utilize audio samples to detect errors and provide feedback on where improvements are needed. This approach aids in developing

listening and pronunciation skills more effectively, allowing learners to refine their speech faster.

Interactive Conversations for Practicing Multiple Languages

AI chatbots assist users in practicing languages through interactive conversations. Learners can engage in dialogue with AI-powered bots, helping them develop their speaking and writing skills in a context that closely mimics real-life scenarios. This method is particularly useful for preparing learners to use the language in everyday situations confidently.

By focusing on pronunciation and conversational practice, AI makes language learning more immersive and practical, empowering learners to achieve fluency with greater ease.

Making the Learning Process Engaging

AI-based games and interactive exercises make language learning enjoyable. Many applications turn language learning into a gamified experience, encouraging users to practice daily. This approach increases interest in the learning process and boosts motivation, helping learners stay consistent in their efforts.

Enhancing Writing and Grammar Skills

AI-powered tools help users identify and correct errors in written language and grammar. These programs play a crucial role in improving writing accuracy and grammatical understanding. Tools like *Grammarly* or *LanguageTool* analyze written text, highlight mistakes, and offer suggestions for better writing. This makes it easier for learners to refine their writing skills and achieve greater proficiency.

By making learning fun and providing practical support for writing, AI ensures a well-rounded and engaging approach to mastering a language.

Multilingual Environment and Contextual Translation

AI enables accurate translation of words and sentences based on context, helping users understand how words and phrases are used in specific situations. This capability not only enhances comprehension but also allows learners to explore multiple languages simultaneously. Multilingual platforms provide contextual translations across various languages, offering learners a broader perspective on language usage.

Improving Listening and Comprehension Skills

AI applications enhance listening skills by exposing users to diverse accents and sounds. By practicing with such tools, learners become better at understanding the language and interpreting speech in real-life conversations. This improves their ability to comprehend spoken language and engage more effectively in discussions with native speakers.

Through contextual learning and active listening practice, AI helps create a more immersive and effective language learning experience.

Umuman olganda, sun'iy intellekt xorijiy tillarni o'rganish jarayonini tez, samarali va oson qilish bilan birga, har bir o'quvchiga o'z ehtiyojlari va qobiliyatlariga moslashgan, qulay va qiziqarli muhitni taqdim etadi.

Analysis of Algorithms Used in AI for Language Learning

The use of artificial intelligence in language learning relies on several core algorithms. These algorithms automate and optimize processes like language analysis, translation, pronunciation evaluation, and comprehension. Below is an in-depth overview of the primary AI algorithms utilized in language learning:

1. Natural Language Processing (NLP)

Natural Language Processing (NLP) is a foundational component of AI that enables computers to understand, analyze, and generate human language. It plays a critical role in various aspects of language learning:

- Language Analysis and Learning:

NLP facilitates the syntactic (grammar) and semantic (meaning) analysis of texts, helping learners understand grammatical structures and the meaning of words in context.

- Text Understanding and Generation:

NLP algorithms can interpret texts and generate appropriate responses, enabling dynamic and meaningful interactions. For instance, this allows AI systems to simulate real-world conversations with learners.

-Language Modeling and Explanation:

Advanced NLP models, such as GPT-3 and GPT-4, can model language and provide detailed explanations of text. They can engage in interactive dialogue with learners, offering a conversational practice environment.

NLP ensures a comprehensive and engaging approach to learning by enabling learners to interact with text and spoken language in meaningful ways.

Do you want to explore more AI algorithms used in this field, such as machine learning techniques or neural networks?

2. Machine Learning (ML)

Machine learning algorithms are fundamental in developing models for language learning based on large datasets of linguistic information. These algorithms include:

- Supervised Learning:

This approach trains AI models using labeled data. For example, grammar-checking tools are trained on extensive datasets of correct and incorrect grammar samples to identify errors effectively.

- Unsupervised Learning:

This method does not require labeled data and is used to identify patterns in text. Language learning applications use it to group words, understand contextual meanings, and suggest vocabulary in different contexts.

- Reinforcement Learning:

In this approach, algorithms improve through interaction with users. Chatbots, for instance, use reinforcement learning to enhance their conversational abilities based on user feedback, creating more natural and engaging dialogue experiences.

3. Deep Learning and Neural Networks

Deep learning algorithms, particularly neural networks, work alongside NLP to enhance the efficiency and accuracy of language learning processes.

-Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs):

RNNs are used to process sequential data like text. Specialized RNNs such as LSTMs (Long Short-Term Memory networks) maintain context over longer sequences, which is crucial for understanding sentences and performing accurate translations.

-Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs):

Though primarily used for image analysis, CNNs are employed in speech recognition systems for tasks like pronunciation evaluation by analyzing audio waveforms.

-Transformer Models:

Transformers, such as BERT and GPT, play a pivotal role in modern NLP tasks. These models analyze the context of words deeply and generate highly accurate and context-sensitive responses, which are essential for language learning applications.

Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR)

ASR algorithms convert spoken language into text and are essential for evaluating pronunciation and providing feedback. These tools analyze learners' speech, identify errors, and offer corrective suggestions, significantly improving listening and speaking skills.

Translation Algorithms

AI-based translation algorithms enable the conversion of text or speech from one language to another while ensuring contextual accuracy. Below are the primary approaches used:

-Statistical Machine Translation (SMT):

SMT relies on large datasets of translated text to compute statistical probabilities for word and phrase translations. While effective for basic

translations, it lacks flexibility and can produce less accurate results, especially for nuanced contexts.

Neural Machine Translation (NMT):

NMT uses neural networks to perform deep contextual analysis of text, delivering higher-quality and more context-aware translations. Advanced translation tools like Google Translate and DeepL use NMT for their exceptional accuracy and adaptability.

Sentiment Analysis

Sentiment analysis evaluates the emotional tone of a text, aiding in understanding cultural and contextual nuances. In language learning, it helps users grasp the intended mood, such as humor, criticism, or positivity. By integrating sentiment analysis, AI can teach learners to interpret subtleties in tone, making the learning experience richer and more culturally informed.

Grammar and Style Analysis

Language learning applications employ AI algorithms to identify grammatical errors and stylistic inconsistencies in users' writing. These tools provide feedback on grammar, word usage, and tone, enhancing writing precision and style.

Popular examples include:

- Grammarly: Highlights grammar, spelling, and stylistic issues with actionable suggestions.
- ProWritingAid: Offers detailed stylistic and structural feedback for improved clarity and conciseness.

These algorithms not only help users write better but also deepen their understanding of language rules, making AI an invaluable companion in mastering a new language.

Conclusion

In general, artificial intelligence (AI) has taken a significant place in the process of learning foreign languages today, demonstrating its effectiveness. AI not only automates teaching but also personalizes the language learning process, adapting to the needs of learners.

Through AI algorithms:

- It creates opportunities for deep understanding of the language, improves pronunciation, and detects grammatical errors.
- Real-time feedback and personalized learning programs allow students to develop their knowledge more effectively.
- AI platforms offer interactive and engaging learning methods, which boosts motivation and makes the process more enjoyable.

Uzbekistan's Approach:

The decree adopted on February 17, 2021, regarding the "Creation of conditions for the rapid implementation of artificial intelligence technologies" encourages the widespread use of AI in the country. This decree is aligned with the "Digital Uzbekistan – 2030" strategy, focusing on the application of digital technologies, including AI, in education. Artificial intelligence is becoming a crucial tool for enhancing global competitiveness, especially in the field of foreign language learning.

Limitations and Prospects:

Although AI technologies make language learning more efficient and adaptable, they still cannot fully replace human thought, cultural understanding, and creativity. Nevertheless, AI continues to evolve as an essential tool for overcoming the challenges of learning complex languages.

In the future, the further development of AI algorithms will enhance the existing language learning systems.

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